

Academic Anxiety among Teenage Girls: An Analytical Approach

¹Shraddha Agrawal,²Dr. Suvidha

¹Research Scholar, ²Associate Professor

^{1,2}Department of Human Development,

Faculty of Home Science, Banasthali Vidyapith, 304022, Rajasthan, India

Abstract:-

Introduction: Academic anxiety is inevitably detrimental to a student's performance if it is unmanageable. Consequently, a student's concern for particular academic pursuits decreases as anxiety increases. High academic anxiety levels hinder students' ability to pay attention and process information. **Objective:** The major objectives of the study were to assess and compare the academic anxiety among 12th-class girls of different academic streams (Arts, Science, and commerce). **Methods:** This research used a survey methodology; the data was collected by using an academic anxiety scale (AAS-SAMRUA) English (New) (2017) by M. Abid Siddiqui and Atieq VR Rehman. The results were interpreted by using frequency, percentage and 't-tests. **Result:** According to the study's findings, none of the students had a extremely low level of academic anxiety, only 10% of students had low academic anxiety and below average academic anxiety, 45% had average academic anxiety, and 94% had above average academic anxiety. Whereas 38% of students came under high academic anxiety and only 3% were falling under extremely high academic anxiety.

Conclusion: According to the t-test results, the null hypothesis "There is a significant difference in anxiety levels among students of Arts and Science as well as Science and Commerce" is rejected. However, the null hypothesis "There is no substantial difference in the degree of anxiety between Arts and Commerce" is acknowledged.

Keywords:- Academic anxiety, Adolescence, academic performance, attentional deficits, cognitive interruptions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescents the most valuable human assets of a country resource are highly exposed to intense competition, rapidly changing societal expectations, cross-cultural influences, etc. Such kind of undue and insurmountable pressure upon their life can be hazardous to their productivity. All of these elements propel the younger generation to live in a state of preoccupation with stress; as a result, they become disoriented and fail to concentrate on their true aims. Young people meet irrational and unconventional expectations, which causes irritation and sometimes more severe misbehaviours like suicide, drug addiction, intolerance, etc. (Sonali, 2018). Empirical findings under various research support the fact that academic anxiety in youngsters exerts a detrimental impact on their overall life and performance.

II. ACADEMIC ANXIETY

Academic anxiety is defined as a fear of academic obligations and it is manifested by academic procrastination and feelings of apprehension towards academic obligations (Hooda & Saini, 2017).

Students' concentration and memory, which are essential for academic achievement, are hampered by academic worry, which can get worse over time. The level of anxiety associated with particular academic activities rises as a student's performance in class declines. Academic anxiety can be brought on by a variety of variables, including personal, familial, social, and institutional ones. Personal factors can include intelligence levels, maladjustment, low self-esteem, health issues, emotional disorders, and more. Low socioeconomic level, lack of supervision, parents' disinterest, and other family issues are examples of familial variables. Social causes include casteism, unfair resource allocation, illiterate neighbourhoods, and arbitrary standards that are imposed on people. Institutional factors may be influenced by the type of school (Government or Private School), the learning environment, the co-curricular activities, the teacher-student connection, and other factors. (Alam*, 2017)

III. ANXIETY ACCOMPANIES SEVERAL EMOTIONS AND MANIFESTATIONS

- **Worry** that prevents someone from focusing on and effectively completing academic assignments. For instance, thinking negatively about oneself, predicting failure, or worrying about the effects of poor performance. Self-hypnosis and arguing negative and self-defeating ideas are two helpful strategies for controlling this component.
- **Emotionality:** Anxiety's biological manifestations. For example, a racing heart, sweaty hands, and muscle tension. Muscle and breathing relaxation techniques are the most efficient ways for dealing with emotions.
- **Task generated interference:** Actions that are related to the task at hand yet are ineffective and hinder successful performance. For instance, spending a lot of time on a test question you can't answer or constantly keeping track of the passing time during an exam. The best management technique is to work together with a study skills instructor or a counsellor to identify the specific habits that are causing problems and design a plan to lessen or alter them. This is because these behaviors can show themselves in a variety of ways.

- **Deficits in study skills:** problems with a person's current study habits that make them anxious are, for instance, last-minute cramming leaves them unable to answer test questions, or poor note-taking during lectures leaves a person unsure of how to approach a crucial task. Many students experience the first three aspects of academic anxiety due to poor study habits.
- **Procrastination:** Procrastination is the act of delaying or postponing something until a later time. Procrastination has an impact on kids' behavioral, psychological, and physical health. Academic procrastination is a type of educational procrastination. A number of negative effects of procrastination have been identified, including stress, concern, a sense of crisis and embarrassment, problems with one's health, a major loss of productivity, and social stigma for breaking promises or obligations. Combining these emotions could lead to increased procrastination. Piers Steel (2010) stated that worry is just as likely to motivate people to start working early as late and that the emphasis of procrastination studies should be impulsiveness. That is, worry will only lead someone to be late if they are impulsive.

IV. ACADEMIC ANXIETY DISORDERS THAT STUDENTS EXPERIENCE INCLUDE

Academic anxiety can often be divided into three categories by educational psychologists, as follows:

- **Severe Academic Anxiety:** This causes students to experience intense, irrational concerns. In fact, among students who are experiencing severe academic anxiety, negative emotions predominate more.
- **Moderate Academic Anxiety:** It is necessary for effective teaching and learning to occur and serves as an inspiration.
- **Mild academic anxiety:** It is manageable without the use of any additional techniques. With mild anxiety, one can easily go about their daily activities.

V. THE COURSE OF ACADEMIC ANXIETY

The abnormal behaviour of a student is displayed at the start of any new academic task, such as procrastinating in academic activities, worrying constantly, performing poorly in schoolwork, failing classes, withdrawing from peer interaction or engaging in activities that they find interesting. Anxiety is often caused by study strategies that students use in their daily academic learning process. Its effects are referred to as "anxiety from the subject," "anxiety from the school environment," "teaching incompetence and partial attitude of teachers inside the classroom," and "sharp competitiveness among students" are a few other factors that contribute to students' academic anxiety. When this happens, it is referred to as teacher-caused anxiety. The introduction of programs like continuous and comprehensive evaluation (CCE) may occasionally cause children to experience extremely high levels of worry. Anxiety from examination refers to stress brought on by Formative and Summative exams. (Rehman, 2016). Finally, pressure from parents causes stress for students at both levels. In their efforts to guide their children, parents can become one of the main sources of stress for students. Peers also put pressure on students in regard to dress, behaviour, friend choices, and many other areas of life, and this pressure can have a significant negative impact on students' well-being. (Rani, 2017)

There are various dimensions of academic anxiety in students mentioned in the below diagram are justified as follows:

THE DIMENSIONS OF ACADEMIC ANXIETY

The following are some reviews that had been studied in order to understand facts related to Academic Anxiety

- Piers Steel (2010) indicated that “anxiety is just as likely to get people to start working early as late and that the focus of studies on procrastination should be impulsiveness. That is anxiety will cause people to delay only if they are impulsive.”
- Ader&Erktin (2012) stated that “Teaching students’ self-regulation can reduce anxiety and increase academic performance.”
- Meetai (2012) indicated that “academic anxiety is a sort of state anxiety which relates to the approaching threat from the academic institution’s environment admitting teachers, certain subjects like mathematics, English etc.
- Dhull and Kumari (2015) conducted a study on “Academic stress among adolescents in relation to gender”. Findings indicated that there is a significant difference between the academic stress of male and female adolescents. Female subjects were found to be under more academic stress as compared to their male counterparts.”
- Kaur and Kaur (2016) conducted a study on “Academic Stress in Relation to Emotional Stability of Adolescent Students”. Results revealed that there is no significant difference between academic stress (academic frustration, academic conflict and academic anxiety) with respect to gender but academic pressure showed a significant difference between boys and girls. Girl participants are found to be more under academic pressure as compared to boys.”
- Yusuph (2016) investigated the “causes and effects of anxiety on the academic performance of secondary students of Domodo, Tanzania. Results revealed that the major cause of anxiety among students was corporal punishment followed by the school milieu and potentials (capabilities) of the students, and a significant number of the students are affected by it. Moreover, there was an

inverse relationship between anxiety and academic performance. Girls were more prone to anxiety as compared to boys.”

- Rehman (2016) carried out “a study to find out the causes of academic anxiety among higher education students and its preventive measures. The findings of the study clearly revealed that there are various potential threats such as personal, familial, institutional, social and political that provoke anxiety among students and clinical and non-clinical measures are available to deal with the anxiety. There is a dire need to spread awareness among the students, parents, and teachers.”

VI. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Participants and procedures

The following study was conducted in a senior secondary school at Banasthali Vidyapith located in District Tonk, Rajasthan. The study's sample included 200 girls in the 12th grade from the Arts, Science, and Commerce streams. The students were selected through a simple random sampling technique, the chit-lottery method. prior permission for that was taken from the principal of the school. Finally 67 students from Arts, Science and Commerce each were taken to derive the sample of 201 girls. The frequency, mean, standard deviation, and t-test were the statistical measures used in the study. The calculation was performed using IBM SPSS statistics 21 version software.

B. Measures

The tool used for data collection was the Academic anxiety scale (AAS-SAMRUA) English (New) (2017) by M. Abid Siddiqui and Atieq VR Rehman. This scale consists of 44 items divided into 6 dimensions such as -academic anxiety symptoms, anxiety from poor study habits, anxiety from a subject, anxiety from the school environment, anxiety from teachers, and anxiety from examination.

VII. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Levels of academic anxiety	Frequency of Students			
	Arts%	Science%	Commerce%	Total%
Extremely High Academic Anxiety	0	0	3	3
High Academic Anxiety	14	12	12	38
Above Average Academic Anxiety	36	25	33	94
Average Academic Anxiety	12	16	17	45
Below Average Academic Anxiety	2	8	0	10
Low Academic Anxiety	2	6	2	10
Extremely Low Academic Anxiety	0	0	0	0

Table 1: Levels of academic anxiety among different streams

The degree of academic anxiety among students from three distinct disciplines. None of the Arts and Science students and about (3%) of Commerce students fell into the first dimension, **Extremely High Academic Anxiety**; whereas (14%) of Arts, (12%) of Science and (12%) of Commerce students were in the second dimension **High Academic Anxiety**; while (36%) of Arts, (25%) of Science and (33%) of Commerce students comes in the category of **Above Average Academic Anxiety**; whereas

(12%) of Arts, (16%) of Science and (17%) of Commerce students comes in the category of **Average Academic Anxiety**. The students who come under **Below Average Academic Anxiety** are (2%) from Arts, (8%) respectively from science and none from Commerce; whereas (2%) of Arts, (6%) of science and (2%) of Commerce students come under the category of **Low Academic Anxiety**. Furthermore, none of the students was found to have an Extremely Low Level of Academic Anxiety.

Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	"t-test"	Significance "P"	Remark
Arts	85.59	8.913	2.075	.000**	Significant
Science	80.19	13.582			
Science	79.92	13.504	3.348	.001**	Significant
Commerce	86.68	9.567			
Arts	85.59	8.913	.572	.449	Not significant
Commerce	86.51	9.537			

Table 2: Level of significance among different streams

** Significant at 0.01 level

*Significant at 0.05 level

The mean score, standard deviation, t-value, and level of significance for each stream are shown in the above table (Arts, science, and Commerce). According to the above table, in the first group, the mean scores of the Arts and science stream on the level of anxiety were 85.59 and 80.19 respectively, the higher means of arts indicate higher anxiety. When the "t-test" was used to compare the scores of both streams, the calculated value was ($t=2.705$, $p.000$), which was significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, it can be inferred that a significant difference was found in the level of anxiety among students of Arts and Science. **Hence, the null hypothesis "There is a significant difference in the level of anxiety among students of Arts and Science" is accepted.** Similarly, in the second group, it has been found that the mean scores of Science and Commerce on level of anxiety were 79.92 and 86.68 respectively. When "t-test" was applied to compare the scores of both streams, it was found that the calculated value was ($t=3.348$, $p<.001$), which was significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, it can be inferred that a significant difference was found in the level of anxiety among students of Science and Commerce, the higher mean of commerce students depicts higher anxiety. **Hence, the null hypothesis "There is a significant difference in the level of anxiety among students of Science and Commerce" is also accepted.** Meanwhile, in the third category, the mean scores for Arts and Commerce on level of anxiety were 85.59 and 86.51, respectively. When the "t-test" was applied to compare scores of both streams, it was found that the calculated value was ($t=.572$, $p>.449$), which was not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, it can be inferred that a significant difference was not there in the level of anxiety among students of Arts and Commerce. **Hence, the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the level of anxiety among students of Arts and Commerce" is rejected.**

VIII. CONCLUSION

The study's findings show a significant difference between students majoring in science and commerce and arts and sciences in terms of anxiety levels. However, the null hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the degree of anxiety between Arts and Commerce" is accepted.

Academic anxiety is a sort of anxiety that can be brought on by a number of things, including bad study habits, the subject, the school environment, teachers, and exam anxiety. The findings show that students' choices of

subjects may be Influenced by their academic anxiety. The children's performance reflects their level of anxiety.

Suggestions for the management of academic anxiety; based on the experiences of research and the review of extensive literature researchers have drawn some effective and practical solutions for dealing with the issues originating from academic anxiety.

- Good practices to be followed by Students
 - Incorporate more anticipation into your life
 - Exercise regularly
 - Surround yourself with people who motivate you
 - Don't compare yourself with others
 - Learn to be assertive and stand up for yourself
 - Avoid isolation
 - Make sure to attend all your classes
 - Learn to study more effectively
 - Find ways to calm down. Take short breaks while studying.
- Good practices to be followed by teachers
 - Limit homework overload
 - Schedule time to organize
 - Listen to their queries
- Good practices to be followed by Parents
 - Ensure the appropriate amount of sleep
 - Serve a healthy diet
 - Model self-care. The best way to incorporate daily exercise, healthy eating habits, and sound sleep in a child's life and parents should also follow them.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study was supported by my esteemed supervisor **Dr Suvidha** (Associate professor), Human Development, Faculty of Home Science, Banasthali Vidyapith.

- **Funding:** This study received no specific financial support.
- **Competing Interests:** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.
- **Transparency:** The authors confirm that in the manuscript an honest, accurate, and transparent account of the study was reported; that no vital features of the study have been omitted; and that any discrepancies from the study as planned have been explained.
- **Ethical:** This study follows all ethical practices during writing.

REFERENCES**Journal**

- [1.] Pizzie, R. G., & Kraemer, D. J. (2019). The academic anxiety inventory: Evidence for dissociable patterns of anxiety related to math and other sources of academic stress. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 2684.
- [2.] Alam, M. (2018). Study of academic anxiety and academic achievement across certain demographic factors. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*, 6(46), 10789-10801
- [3.] Azeem, A. (2018). Study of academic anxiety and academic achievement among secondary school students. *International journal of research in social sciences*, 8(3), 147-161.
- [4.] Sonali, S. (2018). A comparative study of academic stress among senior secondary students enrolled in different streams. *Research Guru*, 12(2), 1038-1053.
- [5.] Rani, M. J. J. (2017). Academic Stress among School Students Writing Board Exam. *International Journal for Advance Research and Development*, 2(1).
- [6.] Hooda, M., & Saini, A. (2017). Academic anxiety: An overview. *Educational Quest*, 8(3), 807-810
- [7.] Alam, M. J. F. (2017). Impact and factors of academic anxiety: A review. *IJARIE International Journal*, 3
- [8.] Hooda, M., & Saini, A. (2017). Academic anxiety: An overview. *Educational Quest*, 8(3), 807-810.
- [9.] Akhtar, D. M. I. (2016). Research design. *Research Design (February 1, 2016)*
- [10.] Jayanthi, P., Thirunavukarasu, M., & Rajkumar, R. (2015). Academic stress and depression among adolescents: A cross-sectional study. *Indian pediatrics*, 52(3), 217-219.
- [11.] Bihari, S. (2014). Academic anxiety among secondary school students with reference to gender, habitat and types of school. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research (IJEPR)*, 3(4), 30-32.
- [12.] Baviskar, M. P., Phalke, V. D., & Phalke, D. B. (2013). Depression, anxiety and stress: A comparative study in arts, commerce & science junior college students in the rural area of India. *GRA*, 2, 183-5.

Website

- [13.] <https://www.calmclinic.com/anxiety/types/mild-anxiety>.

AUTHORS BIOGRAPHY

Shraddha Agrawal has completed her master's from Banasthali Vidyapith and Currently pursuing PhD under the supervision of Dr Suvidha (Associate Professor) Department of Human Development, Faculty of Home Science, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India.

Dr Suvidha is an Associate professor at the Human Development department, Faculty of home science, Banasthali Vidyapith. She has almost 25 years of experience in teaching and research. One DST student project, 35 dissertations and 5 PhDs as research supervisor. Member of faculty and academic counsel for Banasthali and some other universities. Students' personal and career counselling. The main interest areas in research are mental health and its management, adolescent issues, early childhood care and education, special education and reproductive health issues. Near about 27 research papers, and 5 book chapters and participated in many national and international conferences and workshops.